

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Towards an integrated radiofrequency safety concept for implant carriers in MRI based on sensor-equipped implants and parallel transmission

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Funding information

This work has received funding from the European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research (EMPIR) programme and from the European Partnership on Metrology, both co-financed by the Participating States and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant numbers 17IND01 MIMAS and 21NRM05 STASIS.

Abstract

To protect implant carriers in MRI from excessive radiofrequency (RF) heating it has previously been suggested to assess that hazard via sensors on the implant. Other work recommended parallel transmission (pTx) to actively mitigate implant-related heating. Here, both ideas are integrated into one comprehensive safety concept where native pTx safety (without implant) is ensured by state-of-the-art field simulations and the implant-specific hazard is quantified in situ using physical sensors. The concept is demonstrated by electromagnetic simulations performed on a human voxel model with a simplified spinal-cord implant in an eight-channel pTx body coil at 3T. To integrate implant and native safety, the sensor signal must be calibrated in terms of an established safety metric (e.g., specific absorption rate [SAR]). Virtual experiments show that *E*-field and implant-current sensors are well suited for this purpose, while temperature sensors require some caution, and B_1 probes are inadequate. Based on an implant sensor matrix Q_s , constructed in situ from sensor readings, and precomputed native SAR limits, a vector space of safe RF excitations is determined where both global (native) and local (implant-related) safety requirements are satisfied. Within this safe-excitation subspace, the solution with the best image quality in terms of B_1^+ magnitude and homogeneity is then found by a straightforward optimization algorithm. In the investigated example, the optimized pTx shim provides a 3-fold higher mean (B_1^+) magnitude compared with circularly polarized excitation for a maximum implant-related temperature increase $\Delta T_{\text{imp}} \leq 1$ K.

To date, sensor-equipped implants interfaced to a pTx scanner exist as demonstrator items in research labs, but commercial devices are not yet within sight. This paper aims to demonstrate the significant benefits of such an approach and how this could impact implant-related RF safety in MRI. Today, the responsibility for safe implant scanning lies with the implant manufacturer and the MRI operator; within the sensor

Abbreviations used: AIMD, active implantable medical device; CEM43, cumulative equivalent minutes at 43°C; CP, circularly polarized; FDTD, finite-difference time-domain; NTC, negative temperature coefficient; pTx, parallel transmission; PVP, polyvinylpyrrolidone; RF, radiofrequency; RMS, root mean square; ROI, region of interest; SAR, specific absorption rate; VOP, virtual observation point.

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concept, the MRI manufacturer would assume much of the operator's current responsibility.

KEYWORDS

active implantable medical devices, implant safety, parallel transmission, RF heating, simulation, virtual sensor

1 | INTRODUCTION

Safety hazards related to radiofrequency (RF) heating of metallic implants are still a matter of vivid research.¹ Serious accidents have happened, most notably with stimulator electrodes in the brain,^{2,3} and MRI manufacturers—to this day—exclude the scanning of implant carriers in their user's manuals, thus declaring it off-label use. Simultaneously, the number of implant carriers increases and this group cannot generally be excluded from MRI.⁴ Test procedures to quantify RF-heating-related hazards associated with active implantable medical devices (AIMDs), which are the focus of the present paper, are described in ISO/TS 10974.⁵ The implant manufacturers are responsible for demonstrating that their devices are “MR conditional”^{6,7} and to specify permissible scan conditions for their products. It is the sole responsibility of the MRI operator, however, to ensure that an actual patient examination is compliant with the conditions specified during the implant test. While safe MRI examinations on implant-carrying patients are certainly possible in this manner, the described approach is neither failsafe nor effective in exploiting MRI's full potential. This is because the safety limits for a certain AIMD type are defined ex ante, at present, during product development. Neither the specific patient, nor the scanner type and hardware, nor the specific scan conditions, are known at that time. The resulting safety limit is a least-common-denominator solution, disregarding the patient, the scanner, and the imaging goal. Therefore, an alternative approach that overcomes this limitation is desirable: the move from an ex ante implant safety assessment to ensure implant safety in situ.

Such attempts have been made for almost three decades. Frequently, this involves using the MR scanner itself, for example, by measuring B_1^+ or the image phase surrounding the implant^{8–10} or the induced RF currents in the implant.^{11–15} The implant transfer function,¹⁶ enabling an implant-safety assessment via integration of E -fields along the implant path in a simulation without implant can also be determined by MR measurements,¹⁷ and, for its extended form—the transfer matrix^{18,19}—this could in principle also be performed in situ. Finally, various investigations employed MR thermometry to quantify RF-induced temperature increases in the vicinity of metallic implants.^{20–23} RF current and voltage sensors in the scanner's transmit coil allow detecting the current in the implant indirectly via changes in the coil's impedance,^{24,25} and thermoacoustic ultrasound transducers can measure the implant temperature change.^{26–28} To date, however, the latter, conceptually highly interesting examples have never made it beyond proof-of-principle studies, and it remains to be seen how reliably and robustly the quantities of interest can be measured. A limitation of all MR-based methods is the lack of sensitivity to detect and quantify the hazard parameter—such as tip heating—specifying the damage to the patient accurately and quickly. All previously mentioned methods have another, more fundamental limitation in common, in that they restrict themselves to quantifying the hazard but do not provide a policy with which to exploit that measure.

Point-like sensors represent an alternative approach towards in situ assessments of implant safety. Most susceptible to RF-heating are AIMDs, such as pacemakers or stimulation devices with long leads or stimulation electrodes. The induced RF currents in the lead,^{15,24,29,30} and both the E -field³¹ and the temperature near the tip,^{32,33} are measurable using conventional electronic parts. Simple root mean square (RMS) devices (e.g., diodes or thermistors) have been proposed for this purpose, as they measure quickly and sensitively. They are small enough to be implemented close to the implant tip and their reading can be transmitted via the AIMD generator.^{34,35} Recently, it was even demonstrated that the tip E -field can also be measured “remotely” with a sensor in the generator.^{34,36} The essential advantage of local sensor measurements is that they detect and quantify the implant-related patient hazard in situ, under the given scan conditions. The significant safety margins of simulation-only assessments that are required because of the sensitivity of implant hazards even to small changes in implant position or path^{31,37} are thus not needed. In addition, such sensors can serve as safety watchdogs³⁸ and interrupt the scanner in critical situations.

Detecting and quantifying an implant-related hazard is important but solves only a part of the problem. A comprehensive safety concept requires two additional ingredients: (i) scientifically sound and commonly accepted limits for that hazard parameter; and (ii) a recipe of how to utilize that information to ensure a safe scan with the best achievable image quality. Aspect (i) may imply the necessity to calibrate the measured quantity, for example, the RF current in the implant, with respect to another quantity, for example, peak local specific absorption rate (SAR), for which established limits exist.⁷ It must be kept in mind, however, that established safety limits for the native case (without implant) are not always and automatically suited to the implant case as well.³⁹ Aspect (ii) is rarely addressed in the existing literature. The straightforward “solution”, to reduce the average RF power until the hazard parameter falls below an acceptable threshold value, is not convincing as it ignores image quality demands.

Ensuring patient safety while preserving a high mean B_1^+ amplitude for image quality requires additional degrees of freedom for the RF shim. This has been achieved geometrically by aligning the E -field depletion zone of a linearly polarized birdcage body coil with the implant, either electrically⁴⁰ or mechanically,⁴¹ but efficient solutions require a parallel transmission (pTx) system^{42–49} with multiple, independently steerable transmit

channels.^{50,51} Dual-drive birdcage coils have been used to mitigate RF-heating of wire-like implants,^{33,52–55} but more promising results were obtained when more channels were available^{29,56–58} and exploited to optimize patient safety and image quality simultaneously.^{39,51,59–61} While most of the optimizations in former work were based on simulation data alone, there are also a few studies^{30,31,35,62} where a sensor reading was used to determine the pTx settings.

Those extra degrees of freedom come at a price, however, as pTx can also generate SAR and temperature hotspots throughout the exposed body.^{63,64} Specific solutions for this problem have been developed,^{65–67} most notably in the context of 7T MRI,^{50,68–71} but native RF safety is still a field of vivid ongoing research.⁷² The basic methodology (i.e., measurement assisted^{73,74} vs. simulation only^{70,71,75}); the modeling approach (e.g., subject specific^{76–78} vs. static voxel models^{79–81}); the hazard metric (e.g. SAR⁸² vs. volumetric absorption rate⁸³ vs. temperature^{72,82} vs. thermal dose^{84,85}); the thermal model (e.g., Pennes' bioheat equation⁸⁶ vs. generic bioheat transfer model⁸⁷); all these and more ingredients of native RF safety assessments are still evolving and still debated. Native safety is outside the focus of the present work, however, which is why one specific and widely used^{50,67,88–90} approach has been adopted here. This is neither an endorsement nor a requirement, however; the framework proposed here is completely modular; the implementation of native RF safety is just one building block that can easily be exchanged or modified.

What has been missing, to date, is an integrated safety concept for in situ hazard control, locally near the implant and globally in the rest of the body, and simultaneous B_1^+ optimization. Here, such a concept is proposed, combining a state-of-the-art simulation-based safety model for the native case with sensor information quantifying the implant-related hazard. It will be shown how in situ sensor data can be processed on the fly to provide the optimal safe steering conditions for the pTx scanner.

The concept is designed as an alternative to today's Tier 3 assessments as defined in ISO/TS 10974.⁵ It relies on the same assumptions as this state-of-the-art approach, most notably the applicability of the transfer function concept,¹⁶ but offers distinct advantages. To illustrate the proposed concept in detail, an example application of a virtual experiment in a 3T scanner with an eight-channel pTx body coil is presented. For better insight into the problem and to ensure that no potential complications are overlooked, Tier 4 simulations are presented here (i.e., a human body model with the implant embedded is simulated in full). Tier 4 is typically not computationally feasible unless a very simplified implant model is treated. In the present work this is realized by a straight lead with an uninsulated tip touching the spinal cord, mimicking a stimulator device for pain treatment. Despite its simplicity, this dummy implant is fully sufficient to exhibit the problem, a thermal hotspot at a position where in reality it would cause severe damage to the central nervous system, and to investigate the efficacy of the proposed mitigation. In a practical application of the concept, the implant and its trajectory can assume all levels of complexity, because neither Tier 4 nor even Tier 3 simulations need to be performed (only the underlying assumptions of a Tier 3 approach must be fulfilled). While the majority of this paper's results has been obtained by numerical simulations, the critical underlying assumption that the calibration of the primary sensor signal against a hazard measure like temperature is independent of implant path or tip position, has been verified experimentally.

2 | METHODS

The proposed approach is modular, and its building blocks are summarized in Figure 1. Simulations of the case without the implant are used to derive a native safety limit (Figure 1A–C). An implant sensor (Figure 1D) is then used to generate a raw sensor matrix Q_s ³⁵ (Figure 1E), which, in conjunction with a precalculated sensor calibration (Figure 1F), provides an implant safety limit (Figure 1G). Combining both the native and the implant safety limit (Figure 1H) allows for safe B_1 shims (Figure 1I,J). Most of the following subsections can be directly linked to the individual panels of Figure 1. This is indicated in the subsection headings, when appropriate.

2.1 | Field calculations (Figure 1A)

A static pTx shim⁵⁰ of an N_{ch} -channel transmit system is described by a complex vector $\mathbf{u} = (u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{N_{\text{ch}}})^T$, where $U_c = 1 \text{ V} \cdot u_c$ is the complex voltage amplitude of channel c . The complex field $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{r})$ at location $\mathbf{r} = (x, y, z)$ is given by

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{u}) = \sum_{c=1}^{N_{\text{ch}}} u_c \mathcal{E}_c(\mathbf{r}) = \begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{E}_{x,1}(\mathbf{r}) & \dots & \mathcal{E}_{x,N_{\text{ch}}}(\mathbf{r}) \\ \mathcal{E}_{y,1}(\mathbf{r}) & \dots & \mathcal{E}_{y,N_{\text{ch}}}(\mathbf{r}) \\ \mathcal{E}_{z,1}(\mathbf{r}) & \dots & \mathcal{E}_{z,N_{\text{ch}}}(\mathbf{r}) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u_1 \\ \vdots \\ u_{N_{\text{ch}}} \end{pmatrix},$$

where \mathcal{E}_c is the reference electric field if only transmit channel c is excited by $u_c = 1$. Point Q-matrices $\mathbf{Q}_{\text{pt}}(\mathbf{r})$ ^{43,88,91} are calculated as described in Reference.⁸⁸ For any shim vector \mathbf{u} , the point SAR is given by

$$\text{SAR}_{\text{pt}}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{r}) = \frac{\sigma(\mathbf{r})}{2\rho(\mathbf{r})} |\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{r})|^2 = \mathbf{u}^\dagger \frac{\sigma(\mathbf{r})}{2\rho(\mathbf{r})} \mathcal{E}^\dagger(\mathbf{r}) \mathcal{E}(\mathbf{r}) \mathbf{u} \equiv \mathbf{u}^\dagger \mathbf{Q}_{\text{pt}}(\mathbf{r}) \mathbf{u}, \quad (1)$$

FIGURE 1 Methodology. Native safety assessment (A-C) is separated from implant safety assessment (D-G). Combining sensor and native limits (H), pTx shim vectors can be optimized (I-J) in situ. N_{ch} , number of channels; \mathbf{E} , E-field; x, y, z , three-dimensional coordinates; ρ , mass density; σ , electric conductivity; pTx, parallel transmission; SAR, specific absorption rate; carets indicate normalized quantities

where σ and ρ denote the electric conductivity and mass density of the voxels' tissue, respectively. The conjugate transpose is indicated by a \dagger superscript. The transition from “point SAR”, where “point” refers to the grid resolution of the numerical simulations, that is, a three-dimensional volume in the μl range, to the more commonly used mass-averaged SAR, is then performed by averaging the \mathbf{Q}_{pt} matrices accordingly.

2.2 | Safety limits for the native case (Figure 1B)

As a safety model for the native case, the approach of the IEC 60601-2-33 standard⁷ is adopted, where the hazard of pTx MRI is quantified in terms of local and nonlocal SAR with limit values depending on the body region.

The IEC SAR limits (6 min averages) in the “normal mode” are 10W/kg for 10g averaged local SAR in head/torso, 20W/kg for local SAR in the extremities, 2W/kg for body SAR, and 3.2W/kg for head SAR. For a given shim vector \mathbf{u} , mass-averaged Q-matrices \mathbf{Q}_{av} are constructed accordingly, that is, local matrices of every voxel are averaged over 10g while the two global matrices are averaged across the whole head and body, respectively. Normalized matrices $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}$ are defined by dividing each \mathbf{Q}_{av} by its assigned SAR limit; they can be used to calculate the normalized SAR_{10g}, $\widehat{\text{SAR}}$, analogously to Equation (1). The total number of these matrices is $M = N_{vox} + 2$, where $N_{vox} \approx 10^7$ is the number of voxels in the field simulations. In this framework, safe scan conditions for the native case are identical to the requirement

$$\max_{i=1 \dots M} \mathbf{u}^\dagger \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_i \mathbf{u} \leq 1.$$

2.3 | Example application: Patient with a spinal-cord stimulator in a 3 T scanner with an eight-channel pTx body coil

A generic eight-channel pTx birdcage body coil (radius 356 mm; 16 rungs, 352 mm long, 32 mm wide; end-ring width 50 mm; one port per rung, 16 ports per end-ring) was modeled (Figure 2) with dimensions matching approximately the body coil of a commonly used “wide bore” 3T scanner (Magnetom Verio, Siemens Healthineers, Erlangen, Germany).

The human voxel model Duke⁷⁹ with tissue properties from the IT'IS 4.0 database⁹² was inserted in supine position with the heart at the scanner isocenter ($z = 0$ mm). The simulation region was cropped at the knees to limit the computational burden. Two simulations were carried out, one with and one without the implant.

The considered model implant was a straight wire (300 mm length, core: one-dimensional wire as perfect electric conductor⁹³; insulated [relative permittivity $\epsilon_r = 3$] except for 10 mm at the distal tip) that was oriented parallel to the z -axis and that touched the spinal cord at coordinates $x = 0$ mm, $y = -106$ mm, $z = -130$ mm relative to the isocenter. In a simple cable model, the implant's electrical properties would correspond to a physical wire with an inner conductor of 0.83 mm diameter⁹⁴ (see the supporting information A). The voxel mesh had an isotropic resolution of 2 mm.

Complex E - and H -fields of the 48 ports (50Ω voltage sources) of the coil in steady-state were calculated by finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) simulations (Sim4Life 5.0, ZMT Zurich MedTech AG, Zurich, Switzerland) at 128 MHz. An idealized eight-channel coil field configuration was obtained by setting the target voltages for each of the eight channels at each of the 48 ports (1 V at four active ports, 0 V at the remaining 44 ports), followed by electromagnetic cosimulations.⁹⁵ This neglects element-coupling effects that are not relevant for the scope of this paper.

Ten-gram averaged Q-matrices were calculated at each position r by convoluting the point matrices Q_{pt} with a discretized spherical kernel. For simplicity and calculation speed, a uniform tissue density of 1000 kg/m^3 was assumed for averaging, as the difference between SAR and volumetric energy absorption rate is known to be small.⁸³

Thermal simulations were carried out in Sim4Life exploiting Pennes' bioheat equation,⁸⁶ using the same voxel models in the same discretization as the electromagnetic simulations. Calculated electric loss density maps $L(r) = \rho(r)SAR_{pt}(r)$ and published tissue metabolism⁹² were used as heat sources. As is frequently done,^{1,96} a constant blood pool temperature of 37°C was assumed, and heat losses to the environment and thermoregulation were neglected.⁸² Subsequently, temperature maps were generated by simulating 60 min body metabolism without RF followed by 60 min of both body metabolism and constant RF exposure and were denoted as steady-state temperatures T_{ss} . The highest observed $\frac{dT}{dt}|_{t=120\text{ min}}$ was below 3 mK/min.

FIGURE 2 Setup of an eight-channel pTx coil (one channel is marked by a brown ring with four ports in orange), RF shield (gray), and the human voxel model Duke⁷⁹ with a dummy stimulator implant (straight wire, blue) touching the spinal cord (red). The subject is positioned with the central axial slice ($z = 0$) through the heart. The implant is aligned along z and the tip coordinates are $(x, y, z = 0, -106\text{ mm}, -130\text{ mm})$. All example simulations throughout this paper refer to this geometry. The simulation region is cropped at the knees. Left: sagittal slice; right: three-dimensional view. pTx, parallel transmission; RF, radiofrequency

2.4 | Virtual observation points generation and worst-case shim vectors (Figure 1C)

The normalized matrices \hat{Q} for either simulation, with and without implant, are used for separate virtual observation point (VOP) calculations.⁶⁷ The SAR overshoot ε ⁶⁷ is set to 1% of the worst possible local normalized SAR of the native case. The 7.7×10^6 nonzero matrices \hat{Q} are compressed to $N_{\text{VOP,nat}} = 353$ VOPs for the native case and $N_{\text{VOP,imp}} = 327$ VOPs for the implant case, subsequently referred to as “native VOPs” and “implant VOPs”, respectively.

For each VOP m ($1 \leq m \leq N_{\text{VOP,imp}} + N_{\text{VOP,nat}}$) of both simulations, the worst-case shim vector $\mathbf{u}_{\text{wc}}^{(m)}$ is set to the eigenvector belonging to the largest eigenvalue of the respective VOP $\hat{Q}_{\text{VOP}}^{(m)}$.⁹¹ Each of these vectors $\mathbf{u}_{\text{wc}}^{(m)}$ is then scaled with a constant $c^{(m)}$ such that the maximum normalized SAR_{10g} of all $N_{\text{VOP,nat}}$ native VOPs is equal to one:

$$\max_{k=1 \dots N_{\text{VOP,nat}}} \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{\text{wc}}^{(m)\dagger} \hat{Q}_{\text{VOP,nat}}^{(k)} \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{\text{wc}}^{(m)} = 1, \quad \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{\text{wc}}^{(m)} = c^{(m)} \mathbf{u}_{\text{wc}}^{(m)}, \quad 1 \leq m; \leq N_{\text{VOP,imp}} + N_{\text{VOP,nat}}$$

Finally, the resulting shim vectors $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{\text{wc}}^{(m)}$ are used to calculate $m\widehat{\text{SAR}}$, from the uncompressed \hat{Q} matrices via

$$m\widehat{\text{SAR}}(r) \equiv \max_{m=1 \dots N_{\text{VOP,imp}} + N_{\text{VOP,nat}}} \widehat{\text{SAR}}\left(\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{\text{wc}}^{(m)}\right) = \max_{m=1 \dots N_{\text{VOP,imp}} + N_{\text{VOP,nat}}} \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{\text{wc}}^{(m)\dagger} \hat{Q}(r) \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{\text{wc}}^{(m)}. \quad (2)$$

This $m\widehat{\text{SAR}}(r)$ represents an estimate for the maximum of $\widehat{\text{SAR}}$ at position r . By construction, it is guaranteed that $m\widehat{\text{SAR}}(r) \leq 1$ everywhere in the native case, that is, the shim meets the IEC limits, but such limits can be violated, if the implant is added.

2.5 | Suitability test and calibration of possible implant sensors (Figure 1F)

Five physical quantities, the virtual “sensor readings” SAR (denoted as sensor SAR), $|E_z|^2$, $|H|^2$, temperature change-rate dT/dt and induced RF current I_{RF} , were investigated in terms of their ability to provide a measure for implant safety in MRI by exploring how these quantities respond to different pTx shim vectors. To this end, the circularly polarized (CP) mode was applied as a universal reference plus 99 randomly selected shim vectors, all scaled to hit the IEC limits in the native case. A selection of 100 shim vectors is clearly insufficient to scan the 14-dimensional (seven phase differences and seven relative amplitudes after scaling) parameter space and it cannot be ruled out that particularly pathologic cases were not included in the selection. Still, this selection will span the relevant sensor readings and thus can be used to investigate the feasibility of calibrating the sensor and to evaluate if more shim vectors are required.

The sensor readings for SAR, $|E_z|^2$, $|H|^2$, and dT/dt were computed for each shim vector by averaging the simulation results over a cube with edge length 4 mm (2^3 voxels) centered at the implant tip. The induced RF current I_{RF} in the implant was simulated by applying Ampère's circuital law to a quadratic loop of 2×2 voxels around the wire. Two positions were investigated for this sensor, either close to (10 mm) or relatively far away (250 mm) from the tip.

The sensor readings were plotted against four established safety measures, namely, point SAR (SAR_{pt}), SAR_{10g}, implant-induced temperature increase ΔT_{imp} (difference between steady-state temperatures with and without implant), and steady-state temperature T_{ss} . All safety measures were evaluated as their respective maximum value within the tip region of interest (ROI), a 40 mm \times 40 mm \times 80 mm cuboid aligned along the implant and centered at its tip. The ROI was chosen such that it incorporates the full volume around the implant where $m\widehat{\text{SAR}} > 1$ is possible (see below).

To speed up the computations, the thermal simulations were confined to a 100 mm \times 100 mm \times 140 mm box centered at the implant tip. For 15 shim vectors, additional full-space thermal simulations were performed for comparison, and the resulting steady-state temperatures always agreed within 0.1 K everywhere in the ROI (Figure S2). For the maximum temperature that always occurred at the implant tip, differences were below 0.01 K.

2.6 | Experiments on the robustness of the sensor calibration

In real-life applications, the sensor calibration would be performed ex ante by the implant manufacturer. It is thus crucial to ensure that this calibration is robust and universally valid for all patient and implant geometries. To test this, experiments in a pTx testbed³¹ with an eight-channel 7T head coil⁹⁷ and a cylindrical (200 mm diameter, 198 mm height) polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) phantom (relative permittivity $\varepsilon_r = 43.8$, electrical conductivity $\sigma = 0.35$ S/m) were performed.

As a dummy implant, a loop of a semirigid coaxial cable (5 mm uninsulated inner conductor, 12 mm uninsulated outer conductor) was submerged into the phantom according to Figure 3A. An E -field sensor (E1TDSz SNI, SPEAG, Zurich, Switzerland) radial to the coaxial cable and a fiber-optic temperature sensor (FBG/FBG-TEMP-XXS with CANFDX/L-FBG-T8, imc, Berlin, Germany) were attached to the tip (Figure 3C). Thousand RF pulses were fired with 0.1 ms duration and random voltage vectors (but cautiously staying within the linear regime of the E -field probe). The voltage between the inner and outer conductor was measured at the remote end of the implant and recorded together with the corresponding E -field near the tip. Ten shim vectors, covering the full range of possible sensor values, were then selected and successively applied for 60 s to measure the temperature increase. This process was repeated for a second configuration where the “implant” tip was bent ~ 50 mm away from the E -field sensor (Figure 3B,D). The temperature increase was defined as the difference between the mean temperature 5 s before heating and mean temperature from 58 s to 62 s after the start of the heating.

2.7 | Generation of the implant sensor matrix Q_s (Figure 1E)

To integrate the sensor readings into a comprehensive safety assessment combining native and implant related hazards, an implant sensor matrix Q_s is constructed,^{35,59} such that $\mathbf{u}^\dagger Q_s \mathbf{u}$ quantifies the implant-related patient hazard associated with a shim vector \mathbf{u} .

To determine Q_s for an N_{ch} -channel pTx system with a RMS sensor, N_{ch}^2 linear independent shim vectors \mathbf{u}_a ($1 \leq a \leq N_{\text{ch}}^2$) are applied sequentially³⁵; a possible set of vectors is given in the supporting information C. Q_s is then obtained by solving the linear equation system $\mathbf{u}_a^\dagger Q_s \mathbf{u}_a = q_a$, where q_a denotes the respective sensor reading. Q_s is given in units of q_a , such as K, W/kg, or A. For the case of a temperature sensor, Q_s would be identical to the already known T -matrix.^{98,99} Conceptually new is the idea to measure such matrix in situ by a point-like sensor. In analogy to

FIGURE 3 Experimental setup to measure correlation between the tip voltage, radial E -field, and temperature. (A) The dummy implant forming a loop within the phantom with attached fiber-optic sensor. (C) Zoom of (A) with schematic radial E -field sensor orientation. (B) Setup submerged in a cylindrical PVP phantom in position 1 with the implant tip near the E -field probe. (D) The same for position 2 with ~ 50 mm between the implant tip and field probe. PVP, polyvinylpyrrolidone

the native case, a normalized, dimensionless implant sensor matrix $\widehat{Q}_s = Q_s/q_{\text{limit}}$ is introduced, such that any safe shim is described by $\mathbf{u}^T \widehat{Q}_s \mathbf{u} \leq 1$. Unlike the native case, however, the IEC SAR_{10g} limits are not suitable,⁵⁵ see also below, and universally accepted limit values q_{limit} for implants do not yet exist. Different choices for q_{limit} are therefore investigated in the following.

2.8 | Shim vector optimization for B_1^+ quality (Figure 1H,J)

Once the hazard matrices $\widehat{Q}_{\text{VOP,nat}}^{(k)}$ and sensor matrix \widehat{Q}_s are known, the derivation of a static B_1 -shim for implant heating mitigation^{29,89,100} is a straightforward optimization problem. In this work, the Nelder–Mead algorithm¹⁰¹ was applied to minimize a cost function C based on the simulated complex $B_1^+(r)$ maps for each pTx channel:

$$C(S, B_1^+, \lambda) = \begin{cases} \infty & \text{for } S > 1 \\ -\text{mean}(B_1^+) + \lambda \text{CV}(B_1^+) & \text{else} \end{cases}, \quad (3)$$

where

$\lambda \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 5, 10, 20, 80, \infty\}$ is a regularization parameter,

$S = \max(S_{\text{nat}}, S_{\text{imp}})$,

$S_{\text{nat}} = \max_{k=1, \dots, N_{\text{VOP,nat}}} \mathbf{u}^T \widehat{Q}_{\text{VOP,nat}}^{(k)} \mathbf{u}$,

$S_{\text{imp}} = \mathbf{u}^T \widehat{Q}_s \mathbf{u}$, and

$\text{mean}(B_1^+)$ and $\text{CV}(B_1^+)$ are the arithmetic mean and coefficient of variation, respectively, of the magnitude of $B_1^+(r)$ in the image plane (torso without arms).

To illustrate how different choices of the sensor limit q_{limit} affect the resulting $\text{mean}(B_1^+)$ performance of CP and pTx modes, a point-SAR sensor was selected as an example and the optimization was performed for different q_{limit} values. The optimization details are provided in the supporting information D.

In a practical application of the concept, the only computational steps to be performed in situ are the normalization and diagonalization of Q_s , typically an 8×8 matrix, and the solving of the optimization problem. The additional computational load to incorporate the implant is negligible.

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | Single-sided safety assessments

The need for a comprehensive safety assessment, implant plus residual body, is best illustrated by “single-sided” assessments. Figure 4A shows an example of a shim vector designed to keep $\Delta T_{\text{imp}} \leq 0.1\text{K}$ but without a native safety constraint. In the arms (i.e., far away from the implant), a maximum SAR_{10g} of 950 W/kg is found in this case, vastly exceeding any acceptable limit. Only adhering to the native IEC SAR limits, on the other hand, also fails in the presence of an implant. Figure 4B–D shows SAR_{10g}, SAR_{pt}, and T_{ss} near the implant tip for CP shim. While, by construction, SAR_{10g} meets the 10 W/kg limit everywhere (i.e., also at the implant tip), the point SAR exceeds 400 W/kg, resulting in a hazardous steady-state temperature of $T_{\text{ss}} = 41^\circ\text{C}$ at the implant tip touching the spinal cord.

3.2 | Validation of implant hazard confinement and optimum sensor placement

For the given exposure geometry (see Figure 2), maximum intensity projections of $m\widehat{\text{SAR}}(r)$, see Equation (2), are shown in Figure 5. In the native case (Figure 5A–C), IEC SAR limits are, by construction, nowhere exceeded (i.e., $m\widehat{\text{SAR}}(r) \leq 1$ everywhere), while in the implant case (Figure 5D–I), the same shim vectors produce SAR_{10g} values overrunning the IEC limits by factors of up to seven, near the implant.

The zoomed images show that this is indeed confined to a single region of $\sim 15\text{mm}$ radius around the tip. This method allows to identify/confirm hazard-prone regions with their possible SAR overshoot severity and size, and to verify the correct sensor position. In the depicted case, the only critical area is at the uninsulated implant tip, which was used as the point sensor location in the subsequent analysis. If, for a different implant, a secondary hotspot did exist (e.g., further up the device), its presence and location could be revealed by such an analysis and a second sensor might be needed to control that location.

FIGURE 4 (A) Maximum intensity projections of SAR_{10g} for a pTx optimization using only the sensor reading ($\Delta T_{imp} \leq 0.1$ K) as safety measure. By construction, the implant remains cool but this is still a hazardous shim because almost everywhere else in the upper body the IEC limits for SAR_{10g} are vastly exceeded. (B-D) Coronal slices of SAR and temperature distribution around the implant (white line, tip: cross) in the human voxel model Duke for the CP mode shim scaled to reach the IEC normal mode local SAR limit of 10 W/kg. No sensor limit was imposed. (B) SAR_{10g}; (C) Point SAR, please note the logarithmic scale; (D) Steady-state temperature T_{ss} with a maximum of 41°C directly at the spinal cord. CP, circularly polarized; pTx, parallel transmission; SAR, specific absorption rate

FIGURE 5 Maximum intensity projections of $\widehat{mSAR}(r)$, the maximum normalized SAR as defined in Equation (2). Values > 1 indicate regions where the IEC SAR limits are exceeded and are colored in shades of red. The different IEC limits for arms and torso lead to pronounced local steps of \widehat{mSAR} . Human voxel model Duke without (A-C) and with implant (D-F) marked in white with the tip marked by “x”. (G-I) Zoom on the implant region. (J-L) Relative difference between the second and first row on a magnified scale. SAR, specific absorption rate

The maximum normalized SAR differences $m\widehat{SAR}_{imp} - m\widehat{SAR}_{nat}$, depicted on a magnified scale in Figure 5J-L, also reveal some non-local implant effects. The changes of less than 10% away from the implant are safety-wise not relevant; they illustrate that the scattered E -field from the implant slightly alters the field distribution in the entire upper body.

3.3 | Suitability test of possible sensors

For five conceivable sensor types, it was investigated how their output relates to different safety measures (Figure 6).

SAR and $|E_z|^2$ (columns I and II) are linearly correlated to all safety measures and can easily be calibrated in those terms. Such a calibration is not possible with the scatter of $|H|^2$ (column III). The dT/dt sensors (column IV) can be calibrated equally well for a background heating of $T_0 = 37.2^\circ\text{C}$ (e.g., prior to an MR examination). However, if the background temperature increases, as it might do during prolonged RF exposure, the curves shift, which needs to be considered. The implant current I_{RF} (column V) correlates well with all safety measures when measured close to the implant tip. If the distance between sensor and implant tip increases, the sensor's sensitivity decreases, and the noise level increases. A linear correlation still persists, however, even 250 mm away from the tip. It is an interesting side result of Figure 6 that significant differences exist only between the sensor types (columns I-V), while all four safety measures (SAR_{pt}, SAR_{10g}, ΔT_{imp} , T_{ss}) (rows a-d) turn out to behave in a largely equivalent manner.

More quantities considered as field sensors are shown in Figure S3.

FIGURE 6 Correlation of five virtual sensor readings, that is, simulated values of (in principle) measurable physical quantities (columns I-V), with four possible hazard quantifiers (rows a-d). The implant current I_{RF} (V) was determined at the two indicated distances, all other readings directly at the tip (cf. Methods section for details). The different curves for the dT/dt sensor (IV) correspond to different base temperatures T_0 of the surrounding tissue. All data are based on 100 different shim vectors (CP mode and 99 randomly chosen) satisfying the IEC normal mode SAR limits of the native case. CP, circularly polarized; SAR, specific absorption rate

3.4 | Experimental validation of sensor calibration robustness

The experimental calibration curve of the radial E -field as a function of the sensor signal (voltage between inner and outer conductor) for 1000 random shim vectors with a maximum single channel voltage of 0.55 V is shown in Figure 7A. The signals are linearly correlated with the Pearson correlation coefficient $r = 0.969$. Shim vectors exist that result in a near zero E -field at the tip.

The correlation between the measured temperature rise ΔT_{imp} and the squared sensor signal for 10 selected shim vectors with maximum single channel voltage of 2.75 V at two different positions is shown in Figure 7B. While the maximum temperature difference at position 2 is approximately twice as high as for position 1, all the measurements follow the same linear fit with $r = 0.992$, independently of the position of the implant tip.

3.5 | Comparison of B_1 -shims for the native case and implant case

For any given native-safe shim, the sensor reading determines the safety state completely and allows to separate unsafe from safe shims. For the example of a SAR sensor, this is shown in Figure 8A with red and orange dots, respectively. But even within the “safe” manifold where the maximum spatial normalized SAR, $\max_r(\widehat{\text{SAR}}(r)) \approx 1$ (all vectors were scaled to fully exploit the IEC limits in the native case), different classes can be distinguished. All tested shim vectors with a RF-induced temperature increase of $\Delta T_{\text{imp}} \leq 2$ K, for example, form a compact subclass within all safe shims.

Only minor differences in B_1^+ performance ($\leq 10\%$ in the CV and $\leq 5\%$ in the mean of the B_1^+ distribution) are found when applying the same shim vector with and without implant, while $\max_r(\widehat{\text{SAR}}(r))$ can increase by a factor of 8 when the implant is inserted (Figure 8B-E). Safe shim vectors with $\Delta T_{\text{imp}} \leq 2$ K fill nearly the entire available shim subspace for the implant case, however. This indicates that “nearby” any unsafe shim a safe one with similar B_1^+ homogeneity and mean (B_1^+) can be found. The best achievable mean (B_1^+) for implant-safe shims, for instance, is only $\sim 8\%$ below the overall maximum of the native case.

3.6 | Optimization

So far, the parameter space has been explored with random shim vectors. In the following, optimized shims are investigated. In this example, we describe the simplest possible case of static pTx (“ B_1 shimming”) where, except for a global amplitude modulation, the complex voltage vector is kept constant during the RF pulse. The optimization goal is an intense but spatially homogeneous B_1^+ field, here characterized by only two parameters, the mean and CV of B_1^+ in a given ROI. Please note that this is an example, not a restriction. Different pTx applications or more complex optimization goals could easily be incorporated.

FIGURE 7 (A) Correlation of the sensor signal (measured at the remote end of the implant tip) with radial E -field (measured by a probe near the implant tip) for 1000 random shim vectors each with a maximum single channel voltage of 0.55 V. Shim vectors marked with a diamond were scaled by a factor of 5 and are used in (B). (B) Correlation of squared coaxial sensor signal with temperature rise after 60 s of heating for 10 random shim vectors each with a maximum single channel voltage of 2.75 V

FIGURE 8 Evaluation of 20,000 random shim vectors in terms of safety and mean $\langle B_1^+ \rangle$ for both the native and the implant case. All vectors were scaled to fully exploit the IEC normal mode SAR limits if no implant is present. (A) $\max \widehat{\text{SAR}}(r)$ (maximum normalized SAR) versus output of a point SAR sensor. Using the calibration from Figure 6, safe shims with tip $\text{SAR}_{10g} \leq 10 \text{ W/kg}$ (orange) and maximum implant-related temperature rise of $\Delta T_{\text{imp}} \leq 2 \text{ K}$ (blue) can be identified. (B) $\max \widehat{\text{SAR}}(r)$ versus mean $\langle B_1^+ \rangle$ for a subset of 100 shim vectors. The thin lines connect implant and native values for the same shim vector. (D) Same for CV $\langle B_1^+ \rangle$ versus mean $\langle B_1^+ \rangle$. (C and E) Convex hulls of (B) and (D), respectively. SAR, specific absorption rate

FIGURE 9 Image quality for different sensor limits q_{limit} . (A) Preselected sensor limits for a point-SAR sensor (bottom) corresponding to different safety conditions (top). (B) Inverted L-curves with varying tradeoff between highest mean $\langle B_1^+ \rangle$ and lowest CV $\langle B_1^+ \rangle$ for the corresponding optimized shims. For comparison, the CP mode results are also indicated. Note that, for the same image homogeneity, the pTx solution for the most stringent sensor limit (black curve) still allows more mean $\langle B_1^+ \rangle$ than the CP mode for the most lenient case (orange dot). The four shim vectors used in Figure 10 are marked by numbers. CP, circularly polarized; pTx, parallel transmission; SAR, specific absorption rate

Once a safety limit q_{limit} is specified, the tradeoff between high mean $\langle B_1^+ \rangle$ and low CV $\langle B_1^+ \rangle$ can be adjusted by the regularization parameter λ , see Equation (3), as shown by the (inverted) L-curves in Figure 9B. For each q_{limit} , the mean $\langle B_1^+ \rangle$ performance of the CP mode is inferior compared with the corresponding pTx shim.

The advantages of pTx mitigation are particularly evident for lower sensor limits that could be a result of high safety margins in risk management: for the most demanding (and somewhat hypothetical) safety requirement of $\Delta T_{\text{imp}} \leq 0.01 \text{ K}$, the mean $\langle B_1^+ \rangle$ can be increased by a factor of ~ 40 without sacrificing B_1^+ homogeneity, when going from CP mode to pTx. For a more realistic requirement of $\Delta T_{\text{imp}} \leq 1 \text{ K}$, the gain is still a factor of ~ 3 . Alternatively, CV $\langle B_1^+ \rangle$ can be reduced while keeping mean $\langle B_1^+ \rangle$ at the CP mode level. Here, the limits of an eight-channel pTx system are reached, however, at a maximum gain factor of ~ 2 at 3T.

FIGURE 10 Simulated parameter maps for the four selected shim vectors (columns I to IV) marked in Figure 9. (Row a) $|B_1^+|$ in the imaging slice ($z = 0$ mm) with optimization ROI (axial slice through torso without arms) delineated by a white border. (Row b) SAR_{10g} in “tip slice” at $z = -130$ mm. (Row c) Steady-state temperature T_{ss} in the tip slice. (Row d) Amplitudes of the shim vector u_c . The white arrows point to the implant’s x/y position. ROI, region of interest; SAR, specific absorption rate

Four example shims are investigated in more detail in Figure 10. Near the implant, the local B_1^+ -homogeneity is lower for shims with high tip SAR (columns II and IV, “ $SAR_{10g} \leq 10$ W/kg”) compared with low tip SAR shims (columns I and III, “ $\Delta T_{imp} \leq 0.1$ K”). Areas with temperatures exceeding 40°C can be found in the arms (Figure 10IIIc,IVc), even in IEC normal mode. Generally, it is observed that B_1 -shims optimized for high homogeneity require larger variations in the individual channel voltages compared with shims optimized for high mean (B_1^+) (Figure 10IIId,IVd).

3.7 | Point sensor limitations

In Figure 11 it is investigated how well the optimized pTx shims follow the calibration curves for a point-SAR sensor, which were derived based on completely random shims. For the hazard parameter ΔT_{imp} , the data agree well (Figure 11A), but for T_{ss} a deviation occurs (Figure 11B): for sensor-SAR values ≤ 60 W/kg ($\Delta T_{imp} \leq 1$ K), the maximum steady-state temperature lies above the calibration curve (but below 38.5°C). Note that we previously defined T_{ss} as the maximum steady-state temperature within a $40\text{ mm} \times 40\text{ mm} \times 80\text{ mm}$ volume around the tip. If we look directly at the tip, instead, the deviation vanishes (Figure 11C).

4 | DISCUSSION

This work describes a possible new approach to ensure safety for patients with implant in MRI. To use implant sensors for MRI safety purposes has been proposed and implemented previously^{11–15,28,31,33,35,38}; the novelty of the present study is that (i) a variety of conceivable sensors were investigated, and not just a single one; (ii) safety and image quality are consistently treated as an inseparable optimization goal; and (iii) global “native safety” requirements (determined by state-of-the-art precalculations) and local “implant safety” requirements (determined in situ by a sensor on the implant) are integrated within a single concept. The latter is achieved by introducing normalized (and dimensionless) quantities for the native or implant case, which can then be combined to ensure full patient safety, even if different safety measures are used in either subdomain. It was shown that, in addition to providing a subject-specific safety assessment, the sensor data can be exploited for B_1^+ -optimization on pTx systems. The feasibility of the concept is exemplarily demonstrated in silico for body imaging at 3T using an eight-channel pTx body coil and a dummy implant resembling a neurostimulator touching the spinal cord as a critical application.

FIGURE 11 Different safety measures, all related to steady-state temperatures, versus output of a point SAR sensor. Blue dots and line: sensor calibration using 100 random shim vectors (cf. Figure 6). Red dots: 45 optimized shim vectors representing the (inverted) L-curves in Figure 9. (A) Implant-induced temperature increase ΔT_{imp} . (B) Steady-state temperature T_{ss} (maximum value in the ROI). For small sensor readings some optimized shims deviate from the calibration curve. (C) Steady-state value $T_{\text{ss}}^{\text{pt}}$ of the “point tip temperature”. Unlike T_{ss} or ΔT_{imp} , $T_{\text{ss}}^{\text{pt}}$ is evaluated directly at the tip and not as the maximum value within the $40 \text{ mm} \times 40 \text{ mm} \times 80 \text{ mm}$ volume around the tip. The absence of the deviation in (A) and (C) illustrates that it originated not from the tip itself but from the nearby environment. ROI, region of interest; SAR, specific absorption rate

Tier 4 simulations according to ISO/TS 10974⁵ are straightforward to perform for simple straight wires as dummy implants but rapidly become unfeasible when realistic implants with very detailed geometries and a variety of possible trajectories in the body are to be studied. Consequently, a Tier 3–based approach is widely used in real-life safety assessments of AIMDs,¹⁰² which is permissible if and only if the following preconditions are fulfilled: (a) the dominating, implant-related safety hazard must be known to occur at the implant tip; and (b) the transfer-function concept must be applicable, that is, noticeable changes to the preexisting E -field distribution are confined to the vicinity of the implant. For the sensor-based assessment described here, the same conditions apply. A Tier 3 assessment typically consists of the following steps: (i) the implant’s transfer function is measured or simulated, and (ii) it is validated by measuring the response to RF exposure (e.g., in an automated test system¹⁰³); (iii) thousands of possible trajectories are analyzed in precomputed field distributions of multiple possible subject models and various birdcage coils; and finally (iv) a worst-case analysis is carried out by simulating the temperature increase in tissue for the worst SAR cases. The corresponding assessment for sensor-equipped implants would be (I) to calibrate the sensor, that is, to determine the relationship between sensor reading and E -field at the tip in phantom experiments with a dedicated implant testbed (e.g., as described in³¹), corroborated by simulations. An appropriate measurement system would need to incorporate pTx and measure a few implant exposure scenarios. In step (II), detailed simulations of the implant tip region (alternatively: animal experiments) are performed to establish the link between the hazard metric of interest (temperature increase, local SAR, etc.) and the incident E -field. Obviously, step (I) corresponds to the combined steps (i) and (ii) of the Tier 3 assessment, while step (II) corresponds to step (iv). Step (iii) is not needed anymore, with an in situ assessment. In summary, this results in a much simpler safety assessment for the implant manufacturer.

As a side result, the present work confirms that the universally applied safety measure for the native case, $\text{SAR}_{10\text{g}}$,⁷ fails to ensure safety for implants with their locally excessive E -field.³⁹ This is more than the practical problem of determining $\text{SAR}_{10\text{g}}$ at the critical position; as demonstrated in Figure 4, the metric itself is no longer appropriate because implant heating varies on shorter length scales than native RF heating. On the other hand, it was shown that a concept focusing on the implant alone is also inadequate, as unacceptable tissue heating can occur elsewhere in the body.

The implant's response to the actual exposure conditions is determined in situ by measuring the sensor Q-matrix Q_s in a low-power prescan. For eight-channel pTx, this process takes less than 20ms with a diode-sensor.³⁵ Q_s can be compared with the widely applied implant transfer function,¹⁶ which is measured in a phantom or determined by simulations. Once known, the transfer function allows to compute the E -field at the tip by a weighted integration of the tangential E -field along the implant trajectory. Unfortunately, in most cases, neither the E -field distribution nor the implant trajectory is precisely known. Q_s provides the same information, only the (analog) computation is already performed for all possible shim vectors; and as Q_s is measured in situ, it accounts for the actual E -fields and the actual implant trajectory.

The proposed safety concept is modular and kept as general as possible: it is not restricted to a specific sensor type or native safety assessment. For the latter, the maximum product $\max_i \mathbf{u}^\dagger \mathbf{M}_i \mathbf{u}$ of shim vector \mathbf{u} and matrices \mathbf{M}_i was constrained by one. Normalized SAR-VOPs⁶⁷ \hat{Q}_i were used in this work because the IEC SAR limits are currently the most widely used safety metric. SAR could easily be replaced or combined with other metrics, for example, pTx channel power,^{104–106} normalized temperature matrices⁹⁹ \hat{T}_i , or temperature correlation matrices.¹⁰⁷ The integration of a thermal dose concept, for example, cumulative equivalent minutes at 43°C (CEM43),^{84,85,108,109} would not be impossible but less straightforward, as integration over time has to be implemented. More uncertainties like anatomical variance,^{70,110} patient position,¹⁰⁶ or breathing⁷¹ need to be considered. The implementation of such an overarching native safety concept is certainly important, but this is beyond the scope of the present work.

Temperature simulations in this work were based on Pennes' bioheat equation,⁸⁶ which is widely used but has known shortcomings.^{111,112} It can be extended, if needed, by vascular tree simulations^{113–115} or discrete vasculature models.^{116,117} Another alternative is the generic bioheat transfer model,^{87,118} which has been shown to still work well, even when the blood pool temperature increases continuously.^{119,120} While different thermal modeling approaches are likely to result in different steady-state temperatures, the presented concept itself is not expected to change.

The optimization module is another independent block within the concept and can easily be exchanged with a different one, if desired. Dynamic pTx applications like Transmit SENSE,^{42,43} Spokes,^{121,122} or kT-points¹²³ can be implemented, as well as more elaborate cost functions. It is important to note that the concept does not depend on any details of the implant. Trajectory,^{124,125} structural details,^{126,127} proximal termination,^{128,129} etc., will all affect the numerical values within Q_s , but not the validity and applicability of the concept. In this study we chose the straight wire dummy for its computational simplicity, but in real life Q_s will be measured,³⁵ not computed, and no additional difficulties or uncertainties arise if the sensor is attached to a more complex, realistic device.

Of the investigated virtual sensor readings, SAR, $|E_z|^2$, $dT/dt|_{T=37.2^\circ\text{C}}$, and I_{RF}^2 offer good linear correlation with the tested hazard measures. While a direct SAR sensor represents a theoretical construct, an $|E_z|^2$ RMS sensor is representable as a diode.³⁵ For current sensors on wire-like implants, the distance between the sensor and the tip needs to be considered¹³⁰ to avoid problems with null-modes.²⁹ The dT/dt sensor calibration depends on the heating history and thus is not constant over time, which needs to be considered when applied in a safety concept. Regardless of this, temperature sensors have an additional value as an independent watchdog³⁸ and would allow implant tip temperatures to be monitored over time, which could be used in more sophisticated safety concepts, for example, applying CEM43 thermal dose thresholds.^{84,85,108,109} This is also supported by the underlying data of Figure 11. The heating rate dT/dt at the sensor tip can be accurately used for pTx-based mitigations of RF heating showing good linearity (Figure 11A). The highest absolute steady-state temperatures (T_{ss}) below 38.5°C might be influenced by non-implant background heating (Figure 11B), making a direct correlation of the measured sensor signal (Figure 11C) to SAR challenging; however, above temperatures of 39°C, which is a critical threshold for tissue damage based on the CEM43 concept, a linear relationship is found.

While the principal possibility of an implant safety concept based on precalculated native safety limits and an implant limit derived from measurements of a calibrated sensor was demonstrated in this work, more steps are necessary for a practical implementation. Many of the virtual sensors investigated in this work can be translated to realistic implants. It was shown that small RMS sensors such as diodes with dimensions of, for example, $(1.0 \times 0.6 \times 0.65) \text{ mm}^3$, can potentially be embedded in an implant and used successfully for pTx mitigation.³⁵ Similarly, negative temperature coefficient (NTC) thermistors are of small size, for example, $(0.4 \times 0.2 \times 0.2) \text{ mm}^3$ and commercial RF ablation catheters are already available with multiple thermocouples placed at the 7.5 Fr (2.5 mm diameter) tip.¹³¹ Presumably even easier to implement, however, would be a sensor that is located in the AIMD's generator but still senses at the tip. In Figure 7 it is shown that this is indeed feasible if either the implant lead itself can be utilized as a transmit cable or a suitable cable can be added to the lead. These phantom experiments showed that the sensor signal measured at the generator end of the lead correlated well with the temperature rise and E -field as measured by reference probes near the tip. While the implementation of such a "remote" sensor is expected to be much simpler compared with a position right at the tip, additional care must be taken in the calibration process and shielding needs to be considered to avoid measuring stray fields not originating from the tip. Wireless communication between implant and MRI scanner, for example via Bluetooth,³³ needs to be standardized and the respective (cheap) hardware must be integrated. Finally, the software of the MRI scanner must be rewritten to read and to utilize the information from the implant.

4.1 | Limitations

As long as the sensor calibration remains valid, the proposed safety concept applies to all patients, body sizes, and implant trajectories. Nevertheless, up to now we only demonstrated this for a single body model and a single implant geometry. In the results presented so far, hardware

constraints were not considered. These can straightforwardly be incorporated, however, and in Figure S4 an optimization L-curve (cf. Figure 9) is exemplarily calculated for the case of limited RF power.

Because of their additional degrees of freedom, the pTx-optimized shims tolerate stricter sensor limits with less sacrifice in image quality. This effect itself is a general trait of pTx, but the practical benefit depends on many parameters and cannot be predicted from the single investigated exposure scenario. The sensor concept is designed to handle an implant-related hotspot. If this hotspot does not exist (e.g., is prevented by very restrictive sensor limits), the optimization may find solutions that will still be safe, because native safety is built in, but possibly no longer be optimal in terms of B_1^+ .

In this work, sensors were treated on a purely conceptual level. For possible implementations, including the important aspect of measurement uncertainties and the resulting safety margins, the reader is referred to dedicated, sensor-specific publications on this subject.^{11–15,28,31,33,35} An example of how imperfect sensor measurements would affect the predictions of the safety concept is also presented and discussed in Figure S5.

The intention of the present work is to point out the benefits that sensor-equipped implants communicating with a pTx-capable scanner could have and to formalize a conceptual approach to combine native safety and implant safety. This concept benefits the patients, because of a subject- and exposure-specific safety assessment, the MR operators, because the safe scan conditions are now determined automatically and are no longer their responsibility, and the implant and scanner manufacturers, because their mutual responsibilities are well defined and clearly separated, limited to their respective product. The crucial question of the extra costs to equip future AIMDs with such sensors and to establish a communication interface to the scanner must be left to the manufacturers.

5 | CONCLUSION

This work presents an RF-safety concept for implant carriers, separating native from implant-caused hazards. Point-like RMS sensors, calibrated in terms of an accepted hazard metric, enable quantifying the implant-related hazard in situ, for the given patient in the scanner. The combination of fast sensor measurement and precalculated native limits can be exploited in a pTx-shim to achieve the best possible performance under a preselected safety condition. Ultimately, the shim conditions for the safe and efficient scanning of an implant patient would be computed and set automatically, and the MRI operators would no longer be responsible for the RF safety of the scan.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work has received funding from the EMPIR programme and from the European Partnership on Metrology, both co-financed by the Participating States and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant numbers 17IND01 MIMAS and 21NRM05 STASIS. Open Access funding enabled and organized by Projekt DEAL.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

How to cite this article: Petzold J, Schmitter S, Silemek B, et al. Towards an integrated radiofrequency safety concept for implant carriers in MRI based on sensor-equipped implants and parallel transmission. *NMR in Biomedicine*. 2023:e4900. doi:10.1002/nbm.4900